

Impact of Corporate Governance on Firm Performance: Evidence from the Dhaka Stock Exchange

Muhammed Zakir Hossain
*Associate Professor, Department of Business Studies,
State University of Bangladesh, Bangladesh*

Fatema Tuj Johora
Lecturer, Department of Business Studies, State University of Bangladesh

Asif Al Saif
Department of Finance, Jagannath University, Bangladesh

Abstract

In emerging markets, corporate governance has become increasingly significant, as transparency, accountability, and managerial effectiveness are essential for improving the performance of firms. The necessity to investigate the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on the financial outcomes of listed firms has been exacerbated in Bangladesh by regulatory reforms and heightened investor awareness. Consequently, the primary objective of this study is to examine the influence of ownership concentration (OC), audit committee effectiveness (ACE), and board structure (BS) on firm performance (FP) in companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE). The dependent variable in this study is FP, while the independent variables are BS, ACE, and OC. On the basis of established literature, a structured questionnaire was created, and 320 forms were distributed to senior executives, compliance officers, and finance managers of DSE-listed firms. 166 responses were gathered from these, and 154 responses were retained for analysis after screening. The hypotheses were tested at the 5% significance level and correlations were analyzed using SPSS version 26. The results indicate that BS, ACE, and OC have substantial positive impacts on the firm's performance. The paper concludes by proposing potential directions for future research and providing implications for policymakers, corporate leaders, and regulatory bodies.

Keywords: *Corporate Governance, Firm Performance, Board Structure, Audit Committee Effectiveness, Ownership Concentration.*

JEL Classification codes: *G34, L25, M42.*

Suggested citation: Hossain, M.Z., Johora, F.T., & Saif, A.A. (2026). Impact of Corporate Governance on Firm Performance: Evidence from the Dhaka Stock Exchange. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 3(2), 113-125. DOI: 10.59324/ejmeb.2026.3(2).08

Introduction

“Corporate Governance” has been one of the most fashionable issues in modern business management, above all, in those emerging markets like small developing countries where

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

institutional underpinnings, regulatory implementation and market discipline have yet to take roots. The good corporate governance practices are widely accepted to be the major factors, which would promote transparency, accountability and reduce agency problem between the owners and managers. Benefits of effective governance instruments includes the decisions that are taken which should range in accordance with the varied interest that affect stakeholders and thereby result to a performance of organisations (Masrick et al., 2023). In emerging markets, characterized by some strong ownership concentration and controlled monitoring processes the importance of corporate governance is considered to be even more significant.

Bangladesh provides an appropriate environment to explore corporate governance issues as its capital market has grown rapidly and regulatory oversight still undergoing reform. The biggest capital market of the country; Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) witness an elevated participation from firms and increased number of investors in recent years, (Molla et al., 2021). However, despite these efforts, governance issues such as lack of board independence, weak audit oversight and ownership concentration continue to undermine investors' confidence and firm-level effectiveness in Nigeria (Reaz & Arun 2006). These structural flaws weaken internal controls and restrict the capacity of firms to pursue their best interests.

Previous literature highlights that certain corporate governance mechanisms — such as the composition of the board, audit committee quality and ownership concentration — have a significant effect on firm performance. Well-structured board allows the strategic control and it mitigates managerial opportunism through a proper monitoring and advising (Bilal et al., 2019). Furthermore, an efficient and well-functioning audit committee enhances the quality of financial reporting and internal control by decreasing information asymmetry as well as operational risk (Alzeban, 2020). Concentrated ownership that is common in developing countries could also affect firm performance through the effect of aligning monitoring incentives, however it may still depends on context (Emmanuel et al., 2014).

In the context of Bangladesh, there are some available evidences which indicate that governance mechanism is positively related to firm performance but those evidences are still partial (mostly based on secondary financial data) as per Uddin et al. (2021). Furthermore, political interference in board appointments, compliance-oriented governance practices and weak enforcement of governance codes perpetuate the inadequacy of formal systems of governance (Sarkar, 2022). However, these concerns also underscore a need for more empirical research that captures the governance practices at the firm level which exist in the minds of internal decision-makers.

Although there is an increasing focus on governance reforms, in Bangladesh there are few empirical studies that have investigated the joint effects of board composition, audit committee efficiency and ownership concentration on the performance of firms. Especially, perception-related evidence from executives and governance practitioners has been neglected in the literature. Filling up this void, the aim of the current paper is to investigate how these principle governance mechanisms shape firm performance for listed firms in Dhaka Stock Exchange.

Accordingly, the study is guided by the following research question:

To what extent do board structure, audit committee effectiveness, and ownership concentration influence firm performance among DSE-listed companies?

This study makes several contributions to the existing literature. First, it provides empirical evidence on the governance–performance relationship within an emerging market characterized by concentrated ownership and evolving regulatory practices. Second, it jointly examines board structure, audit committee effectiveness, and ownership concentration, offering a more integrated understanding of internal governance mechanisms. Third, by utilizing survey-based data from governance-related professionals, the study offers practical insights for policymakers, regulators,

and corporate leaders seeking to strengthen governance practices and enhance firm performance in Bangladesh.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 1 reviews relevant literature and develops the research hypotheses. Section 2 outlines the research methodology. Section 3 presents the empirical results. Section 4 discusses the findings and their implications. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study and suggests directions for future research.

Literature Review

Corporate governance has evolved as a key platform on which to enable effective monitoring, responsibility and value generation within contemporary corporations, particularly in the context of emerging economies where institutional constraints frequently impede market discipline. Theoretical views such as agency theory argue that control mechanisms must be imposed in order to reduce conflicts of interest between managers and stockholders by improving monitoring systems and aligning incentives. Amongst the legal and enforcement system that are stronger market economy also have relatively less asymmetry of information, therefore internal governance mechanism had plays a less fundamental role in determining firm performance. A result of the focus on governance impact on firm performance within emerging capital markets is that empirical scholars have been looking for those governance features that would enhance firm performance in developing capital markets.

Board structure is one of the most powerful internal mechanisms that can be utilized to monitor and supervise managers in corporate governance context. Board Composition Conceptually, board composition refers to characteristics of the board itself (i.e., the size of the board, independence, diversity and expertise) that will influence its capacity... acting statesmen. According to agency theory an effective board reduces the managerial opportunism by exerting independent judgement and protecting shareholders' interests. This viewpoint is confirmed in practice where following literature a properly constituted and independent...way enhances firm performance through the quality of decisions and increases the monitoring capabilities of the board (Krishnan & Visvanathan, 2007). Skilled and independent directors lead a board well-equipped to question management and mandate adherence to governance standards thus making operations more efficient.

Previous research also indicates that board effectiveness is closely associated with company performance, resulting from superior governance quality and strategic leadership. Studies carried out in emerging markets show that board profile attributes like independence and expertise have a significant impact on financial and non-financial results (Mohammadi et al., 2020). Board diversity and expertise increase access to diverse views and resources that facilitate innovation and long-term value generation. However, unusually large boards can lead to decreased efficiency with coordination and communication also tending to become a potential barrier for performance which necessitating the need to retain an optimal board structure (Raimo et al., 2020). In relation to improving firm performance, then, these results indicate that firm performance is sensitive to the composition of the board.

In such emerging markets like Bangladesh, where role of state is changing to the market they become more relevant particularly in context of concentration and power as; board structure becomes crucial in an environment where regulatory control is limited. Research findings show that firm use more internal governance mechanisms to offset lower level of external governance in a weaker institution setting. Evidence from other emerging markets also documents that independent and professionally diverse boards are related to increased transparency, less agency

costs, and firm performance (Oussii & Taktak, 2018). These observations confirm the notion that board composition has a considerable influence on company performance of DSE-its companies.

Another key driver of corporate governance is the effectiveness of the audit committee as it has association with both financial reporting quality and internal control structures (Abdullah, 2018). The role of an audit committee is a specialized subcommittee of the board that oversees financial reporting and disclosure, ensures independence and objectivity in communicating with external auditors, and maintains oversight of the internal control process. Among other things, functions of an effective AC is to act as a watchdog for investor by increasing the reliability of financial reporting and reducing earnings management to meet accounting standard. Earlier studies stress that the more independent, financially literate and active the audit committee members are, the better they perform to discharge their oversight role (Ismail et al., 2022).

Positive relationship between Audit committee effectiveness and performance Empirical evidence consistently shows positive association between audit committee effectiveness and firm performance. Well-functioning audit committees enhance internal governance by enhancing financial transparency and mitigating information asymmetry, which in then turns can lead to investor confidence and market valuation incensement. The literature suggests that firms with financially competent AC are more likely to detect aggressive reporting and have effective internal controls in place (Velte, 2018). In addition, the more often audit committee meetings held and their proactive monitoring practices would improve governance mechanism and decrease financial misstatements (Kusumosari & Rahardjo, 2023). Together, these mechanisms help improve firm performance by encouraging accountability and operational discipline.

The effectiveness of the audit committee is even more important in emerging markets, where concerns over audit quality and regulation enforcement are perennial. Evidence from emerging markets shows that effective audit committees act as a substitute for external governance mechanisms where such mechanisms are less effective (Bii and Kinuthia, 2024). Through its facilitation of oversight and minimization of financial improprieties, a strong audit committee adds to firm stability and performance. These results lead us to develop a good theoretical and empirical foundation for analyzing the effect of AC effectiveness on Bangladeshi capital market.

Concentration of ownership is a unique characteristic of the corporate governance structure in EMs, and has sparked significant interest among scholars (Dharmapala et al., 2011) as its impact on firm performance is uncertain. Ownership concentration is the degree of share ownership by large shareholders, families, and institutional investors that may have a direct or indirect control over firms' management decisions. If we use agency theory to reason, if big shareholder holds more shares they can monitor deeply and effectively on managers (Lin et al., 2006). When controlling shareholders hold a significant portion of the equity capital, their economic power drives them to enhance their managerial performance and raises firm value.

The literature has shown that ownership concentration can have a positive effect on the performance of companies through enhanced monitoring and alignment of interests with those of shareholders. Research shows that a concentrated owner structure contributes to firm value in countries whose external governance mechanism is weak (Hoitash et al., 2009). Strong shareholders may more actively engage in governance mechanisms to counter excessive management opportunism and enhance strategic decision-making. On the other hand, high concentrated ownership can also lead to entrenchment issue as the controlling shareholder seeks for private benefits at the cost of minority shareholders and may on turn reduce firm performance (Lisic et al., 2019).

Thus, the impact of ownership concentration on firm performance is very much context-dependent. In developing countries like Bangladesh, where laws protecting the interest of minority

shareholders are not strong enough to protect them, concentrated ownership is used as an internal governance mechanism which may be a substitute for competitive (stock) markets in serving as a disciplinary mechanism. Findings from previous empirical studies in the same institutional environment indicate that ownership concentration is positively related to firm performance when powerful blockholders actively monitor and govern firms (Pernamasari & Chariri, 2024). Such evidence confirms the proposition that greater ownership concentration may be conducive to improving firm performance in the context of Bangladesh.

Overall, the previous studies emphasize that board composition, audit committee effectiveness and ownership concentration are some of the major internal governance mechanisms shaping firm performance. Although previous research has addressed the relationships between these variables, a small amount of work has considered their combined impact simultaneously in the context of Bangladeshi capital market. Furthermore, most prior work is built off archived data and does not fully explore the perceptual perspectives of corporate decision makers. Filling this research gap, the current essay incorporates these three governance devices into a single framework to test them empirically in the context of firm performance for firms traded on Dhaka Stock Exchange.

Objectives and Hypotheses Development

The primary objective of this study is to examine whether board structure (BS), audit committee effectiveness (ACE), and ownership concentration (OC) significantly influence firm performance (FP) among companies listed on the Dhaka Stock Exchange. Although corporate governance issues have received increased attention in Bangladesh, limited empirical studies have jointly investigated these governance mechanisms and their impact on performance. Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

- H1:** Board structure (BS) has a significant positive impact on firm performance.
- H2:** Audit committee effectiveness (ACE) has a significant positive impact on firm performance.
- H3:** Ownership concentration (OC) has a significant positive impact on firm performance.

Research Model of the Study

Based on the literature review and development of hypotheses, the study proposes the research model (see Figure 1). Each independent variable is hypothesized to have a **direct and positive effect** on firm performance.

Figure 1. Research Model of the Study

Methodology

The objectives of the paper are to investigate the effects of Board Structure (BS), Audit Committee Effectiveness (ACE) and Ownership Concentration (OC) on Firm Performance (FP) of Dhaka

Stock Exchange (DSE). For this research purpose, we selected by choice some executives and managers who were directly related to finance, compliance, and accounting or corporate governance position within listed firms. As the total population size of corporate governance-related respondents in DSE-listed companies was unknown, a non-probability random sampling technique was used in the study. On the basis of existing literature, a questionnaire was formulated and circulated among 320 staff members employed on various listed firms in different industries. A total of 320 questionnaires were distributed and 166 responses received, with 12 excluded as incomplete or missing data. Thus, out of 174 responses, only 154 were found to be appropriate for data analysis and taken as the final sample size in the study.

The questionnaire items of each variable were extracted from the established corporate governance and financial performance literature. For internal consistency, a Cronbach's alpha was used with $\alpha \geq 0.70$ indicating acceptable reliability. The Structure (BS) construct board was developed from current board scales, and included four items. Reliability of the construct was found to be acceptable ($\alpha = 0.814$). Audit committee effectiveness (ACE) was defined based on audit governance frameworks and measured by four items. The reliability of the construct was found to be high ($\alpha = 0.832$). Ownership concentration (OC): OC was assessed with four items from ownership structure literature with good reliability ($\alpha = 0.789$). The dependent variable FP was derived from previous performance measurement research and measured using three items. All scale items were scored with a five-point Likert scale anchored by '5' ('Strongly satisfied') and '1' ('Strongly dissatisfied').

The questionnaire was made up of two principal sections. Section one collected demographics and professional attributes, such as age, gender, job title held by respondents, work experience and department of service of respondents; sector of business of the firm. The second part consisted of Likert-scaled questions which tapped on the variables employed in this study. For data analysis, SPSS software version 26 was used. Demographic characteristics were presented as descriptive statistics for the information of analysis, correlation analysis to analyze relationship between variables and multiple regression analysis to confirm hypothesis at 5% significance level.

Results

Demographic Statistics of Respondents

100 75 Executives/managers that serve in diverse corporate governance related areas of DSE-listed companies, constituted the sample of this study ($n = 154$). Of the 320 questionnaires distributed, 166 were returned and, after discarding 12 incomplete questionnaires, with a final total of 154 eligible respondents for analysis. Demographic attributes of the respondents participating in the study are shown on table 1.

Table 1 reveals that respondents were overwhelmingly male (78.6% versus 21.4% being female). In terms of age 29.9% and 46.1% were aged 21-30 and 31-40 years respectively, while category of other response to this question constitutes about 17.5%. Only 6.5% were more than 50 years old. With respect to job rank, 35.1% of the respondents were mid-level managers; 44.8%, senior officers; and 20.1% had managerial or senior managerial positions. With respect to work experience, 41.6% had '0-5 years' of experience, 32.5% had '6-10 years,' and the remaining 25.9% had over 10 years of experience. Furthermore, 38.3% of the respondents were from manufacturing, 27.9%, finance; 22.7%, service; and 11.0%, pharmaceuticals & others business sector.

Table 1. Demographic Information of Respondents

Demographic Information	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age		
21–30 years	46	29.9
31–40 years	71	46.1
41–50 years	27	17.5
Above 50 years	10	6.5
Gender		
Male	121	78.6
Female	33	21.4
Job Position		
Junior/Mid-level Executive	54	35.1
Senior Officer	69	44.8
Manager/Senior Manager	31	20.1
Years of Experience		
0–5 years	64	41.6
6–10 years	50	32.5
More than 10 years	40	25.9
Industry Sector		
Manufacturing	59	38.3
Financial Institutions	43	27.9
Services	35	22.7
Pharmaceuticals & Others	17	11.0

Correlation Analysis

The correlation between the dependent variable (FP) and independent variables (BS, ACE, OC) is analyzed in Table 2. Table 2 shows that there are all the three independent variables which have significant positive relationships between firm performance $p < 0.01$ significance level.

There is a solid correlation between the board structure (BS) and company performance ($r = 0.452$). The correlation between audit committee effectiveness (ACE) and firm performance is moderately strong as well ($r = 0.428$). OC is positively related to firm performance ($r = 0.401$). Among these variables, BS has the strongest relationship with FP in our study.

Table 2. Correlation Analysis

Variables	Mean	FP	BS	ACE	OC
1. Firm Performance (FP)	3.9214	1	–	–	–
2. Board Structure (BS)	4.0545	0.452**	1	–	–
3. Audit Committee Effectiveness (ACE)	3.9922	0.428**	0.533**	1	–
4. Ownership Concentration (OC)	3.8571	0.401**	0.462**	0.475**	1

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); $n = 154$.

Hypotheses Testing and Regression Analysis

The estimated coefficients are presented in Table 3. Durbin–Watson statistic value of 1.713 falls between the acceptable bound value ranges of 1.5 to 2.5, which means that there is no autocorrelation problem in the dataset. Scores of VIFs for the predictors were below 5.00, and tolerances between them were within a recommended value (0.1–1.0) indicating there is no multicollinearity problem.

For the model, a R^2 value of 0.368 means that 36.8 percent is explained by BS, ACE and OC combined on firm performance. Table 3 also reveals that all three hypotheses of the research were

supported, because positive significant (at $p \leq .05$) effects of all independent variables on firm performance were found.

Table 3. Regression Analysis

Independent Variables	β value	t-value	Sig.	Tolerance	VIF
Board Structure (BS)	0.301	3.951	0.000***	0.551	1.816
Audit Committee Effectiveness (ACE)	0.276	3.688	0.001**	0.529	1.891
Ownership Concentration (OC)	0.239	3.214	0.002**	0.647	1.545

Note: $R^2 = 0.368$; Durbin–Watson = 1.713. Dependent Variable: Firm Performance (FP). $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$.

Figure 2. Result Analysis of Regression Coefficient

Table 4. Summary of Hypothesis Testing

Proposed Hypotheses	Decision
H1: Board structure (BS) has a significant impact on firm performance.	Accepted
H2: Audit committee effectiveness (ACE) has a significant impact on firm performance.	Accepted
H3: Ownership concentration (OC) has a significant impact on firm performance.	Accepted

Discussion and Implications

This study offers empirical evidence regarding the association between corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance in an emerging market. Through simultaneous looking at board structure, effectiveness of audit committee and ownership concentration, the paper provides an inclusive view about how internal governance mechanisms affect firm performance in context of firms listed in the Dhaka Stock Exchange. Overall, the explanatory power of the model is moderate but substantial ($R^2 = 0.368$), meaning that the included governance mechanisms jointly explain 36.8 percent of variance in performance at firm level. This result supports the assertion in the corporate governance literature that internal governance systems matter and have a significant impact on firm outcomes, especially in environments where external governance structures are relatively weak.

Empirical results show that among governance variables studied, board structure exerts the most significant impact on corporate performance. The results from regression analysis are consistent with our previous findings and show a significantly positive relationship between board structure and firm performance ($\beta = 0.301$, $t = 3.951$; $p < 0.01$) and correlation analysis also confirms this point of view ($r=0.452$, $p < 0.01$). These results imply that well-governed boards of firms –with the proper composition, independent members, and expert capabilities- are more capable of overseeing

management and monitoring control on strategic behavior. This finding is consistent with what agency theory suggests: that active board mitigates the agency problem through monitoring and aligning managerial behavior with shareholders' interest. The finding is also in line with earlier empirical findings that strong board mechanism improves the quality of governance and firm's performance in developing countries where managerial discretion and dominant ownership are more prevalent (Bilal et al., 2019; Mohammadi et al., 2020).

Given the shifting focus of regulatory enforcement and use of special audit reports involving concentrated ownership in Bangladesh, board structure may be important. Effective boards can to some extent offset the weaknesses of institutions and ensure greater transparency and accountability in companies. The evidence seems to indicate that diligent and independent boards serve as governance mechanisms to address the agency problems created by political motivated appointments and weak compliance culture, which previous studies identified in the context of corporate Bangladesh (Reaz & Arun, 2006). Thus, enhancing board structure seems to play an important role as a governance mechanism which may be addressed toward improving firms' performance in the DSE-listed companies.

The findings also provide evidence that audit committee effectiveness has a significant positive impact on firm performance ($\beta = 0.276$, $t = 3.688$, $p < 0.01$), and there is a moderate-strong correlation with firm performance ($r = 0.428$, $p < 0.01$). This result reflects the function of audit committee as subcommittee of board in charge for monitoring financial reporting and internal control. Strong audit committees serve to increase financial credibility, mitigate information asymmetry, and boost investor confidence, all of which enhance firm performance. The finding is inline with past study emphasis that, audit committee with financial expertise independence and active participation are critical toward strengthening governance effectiveness (Alzeban, 2020; Ismail et al., 2022).

In developing countries like Bangladesh, where issues of AQL and AQE continue to be a concern, the role of AC is particularly important. The positive association found in this study indicates that strong audit committees can play the role of an internal mechanic for fiscal mismanagement and governance lapses. This result is in line with the previous assertion that audit committees represent compensatory governance mechanisms in cases where external monitoring and regulatory oversight are weak (Bii & Kinuthia, 2024). Hence, businesses that invest in developing effective audit committee mechanisms are more likely to benefit from better performance results by ensuring that these enhanced financial discipline and governance monitoring efforts ensue.

Meanwhile, ownership concentration also indicates a positive significant impact on firm performance ($\beta = 0.239$, $t = 3.214$, $p < 0.01$) and is accompanied with the positive correlation coefficient ($r = 0.401$, $p < 0.01$). This implies that concentrated ownership significantly has positive influence on firm performance in Bangladesh. From the lens of agency theory, this finding suggests that blockholders are effective in monitoring to alleviate managerial opportunism and align management decisions with shareholder value. In markets with poor protection for minority shareholders, concentrated ownership could also serve as an effective internal governance mechanism by increasing supervision and monitoring (Lin et al., 2006).

The positive impact of ownership concentration found in this study is in line with empirical research on the effect of concentrated ownership in emerging countries where external governance mechanisms are less developed (Hoitash et al., 2009). In Bangladesh, where families dominate and institutions have ownership, large shareholders are well motivated and able to monitor management closely. Although the concentration of ownership confers some problems such as entrenchment and expropriation, it is found overall that monitoring benefits could be greater than potential costs in the DSE-Listed firms. This is in line with the contention that ownership

concentration can be value-increasing as it provides incentives for controlling shareholders to involve more in monitoring (Pernamasari & Chariri, 2014).

The findings of this study have critical implications for corporate executive management, and the securities regulators as well as policy makers. Management wise they suggest that there is still potential for the corporate governance systems to improve when seeking superior company performance. Create more effective boards² of Corporate boards should champion ncreased board effectiveness—independen ce, expertise and diversity can enhance strategic over-sight and accountability. Similarly, resistance to the effectiveness of audit committee such as financial knowledge, independence and meeting frequency could exert a significant impact on governance efficiency and effectiveness. These enhancements in governance to emerging market companies which rely on internal controls, even more important.

Given regulations and policy, our results suggest that for governance mechanisms to function regulators must do more than just comply with policies, they also must be effective. Regulators should enforce governance codes on board composition and audit committee procedure, crackdown on opaque ownership structures, and support incorporated firms with generous tax incentives. In light of the value-enhancing aspect of ownership concentration revealed in this paper, it would be desirable for regulators to decide a sort of an equilibrium or trade-off balance between monitoring benefits due to concentrated ownership and the safeguards that minority shareholders receive against potential expropriation. Such equilibrium-coexistent corporate governance mechanisms can be conducive to achieving sustainable firm operation under high level of investor confidence in capital markets.

To conclude, the evidence indicates that a corporate governance system with more strictness needs to be in place for better performance of firms in its economy. Through the empirical linking of board structure, audit committee effectiveness and ownership concentration with corporate performance this enables the study to provide some empirically based grounds for reinforcing corporate governance in EMs.

Conclusion

The study examined the effect of board structure (BS), audit committee effectiveness (ACE) and ownership concentration (OC) on firm performance (FP) for the listed firms that participated with Dhaka Stock Exchange. As evidenced by the correlation and regression analyses, BS, ACE and OC are significant predictors of firm's performance. The results suggest that the three measures of corporate governance (CG) are all significant at the 1% level with respect to FP. These results indicate that well-designed boards, powerful audit committees, and reasonable ownership concentration are related to superior firm performance.

With the increasing emphasis on corporate governance reforms in Bangladesh, this study raises several issues community of practice that how better and efficiently can raise its standard by impact on DSE listed firms. Firms are called upon to improve board composition by benchmarking minimum requirements of independence, gender diversity, and expertise to enhance strategic monitoring. Enhancing audit committee effectiveness is also important, particularly through frequent meetings, financial expertise and independence from management practicability. Second and more significantly, ownership concentration should be solved so as to optimise monitoring effectiveness while not at the same time harming minority shareholder welfare. Overall, the findings suggest that strong governance mechanisms greatly impact firm performance, which is of utmost importance to the well-being and credibility of capital markets.

Future Research Directions

This research is preliminary and additional study is warranted. First, the quantitative analysis in SPSS was used as a tool for testing hypotheses derived from the perception of respondents. In addition, interviews with the board members, auditors or institutional investors could be employed in future studies to provide a qualitative insight into governance processes and their outcomes. Second, only three corporate governance attributes (BS, ACE and OC) were taken into account in our study while other significant control variables (such as board gender diversity, CEO duality, audit quality or internal control) have been overlooked. Further studies could include these other covariates to help round the final conclusion. Third, the sample was from a stock exchange specifically, that is, DSE. A way to generalize the result further in future research might be to compare listed firms with non-listed ones, or several industries. Cross national comparisons which involve emerging regional markets are also necessary to have more granular insights into links between governance and performance.

References

- Abdel Megeid, N. S. (2023). *Does the relationship between board gender diversity, other effective board characteristics, and audit quality traits affect the 2Fs: Financial performance and financial structure? Evidence from Egypt*. College of Management and Technology, Arab Academy for Science, Technology and Maritime Transport. Manuscript in preparation. <https://doi.org/10.21608/naus.2023.329482>
- Abdullah, S., Aziz, A., & Azani, A. (2022). The effect of board independence, gender diversity and board size on firm performance in Malaysia. *Journal of Social Economics Research*, 9(4), 179–192. <https://doi.org/10.18488/35.v9i4.3226>
- Almuzaiqer, M. (2018). Timeliness of financial reporting and audit committee effectiveness: Evidence from UAE. *Unimas Review of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.33736/uraf.931.2018>
- Alzeban, A. (2020). The relationship between the audit committee, internal audit and firm performance. *Journal of Applied Accounting Research*, 21(3), 437–454. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jaar-03-2019-0054>
- Begum, M. (2025). Company performance and corporate governance in emerging economy: Evidence from textile industries of Bangladesh. *JUJBR*, 25(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.53461/jujbr.v25i01.87>
- Bii, P., & Kinuthia, P. (2024). Effects of audit committee on fraudulent financial reporting among listed firms in Kenya. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 7(4). <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v7-i4-03>
- Bilal, M., Fatima, S., & Abbas, A. (2019). Unlocking the role of corporate boards in stimulating corporate governance. *Global Social Sciences Review*, 4(2), 350–355. [https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2019\(iv-ii\).45](https://doi.org/10.31703/gssr.2019(iv-ii).45)
- Chakraborty, R., & Dey, S. (2023). The effects of corporate governance mechanisms on voluntary corporate carbon disclosures: Evidence from an emerging economy. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 41(3), 1020–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeas-09-2022-0209>
- Emmanuel, U., Ayorinde, B., & Oyewo, B. (2014). Audit committee multiple directorships and financial reporting quality in Nigeria: An evaluation of the interconnectedness using empirical evidence. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2014.v5n20p628>

- Hoitash, U., Hoitash, R., & Bedard, J. C. (2009). Corporate governance and internal control over financial reporting: A comparison of regulatory regimes. *The Accounting Review*, 84(3), 839–867. <https://doi.org/10.2308/accr.2009.84.3.839>
- Hossain, M. Z., Enam, F., & Hasan, M. R. (2017). The role of corporate governance and corporate social responsibility practices in organizational excellence: The case of Grameen Bank. *Open Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 119–130. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojbm.2017.51011>
- Hossain, M. Z., Rashed, M. J. R., Hredoy, A. I., & Tazin, F. (2026). Corporate governance quality and its influence on sustainability reporting accuracy. *European Journal of Innovative Studies and Sustainability*, 2(1), 79–92. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2\(1\).04](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejiss.2026.2(1).04)
- Hossain, M. Z., Urme, U. N., & Hossain, S. (2025). Corporate governance in action: How DHL integrates accountability and corporate social responsibility for sustainable growth. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 2(2), 36–50. [https://doi.org/10.59324/stss.2025.2\(2\).03](https://doi.org/10.59324/stss.2025.2(2).03)
- Hossain, M., Hasan, L., & Hasan, M. (2024). Corporate governance as a global phenomenon: Evolution, theoretical foundations, and practical implications. *Journal of Financial Risk Management*, 13, 342–375. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jfrm.2024.132017>
- Hossain, M., Rahman, F., Golder, U., & Kabir, S. (2025). Effectiveness of internal corporate governance mechanisms in controlling non-performing loans of an emerging economy. *Schmalenbach Journal of Business Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41471-025-00216-7>
- Hossain, M.Z., Rashed, M.J.R., & Hredoy, A.I. (2025). Corporate Governance and Financial Reporting Quality: Mediating Roles of Internal Controls, Ethics, and Regulatory Compliance. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 67-80. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejahss.2025.2\(6\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(6).08)
- Ismail, R., Saleh, N. M., & Yaakob, R. (2022). Audit committee effectiveness, internal audit function and financial reporting lag: Evidence from Malaysia. *Asian Academy of Management Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 18(2). <https://doi.org/10.21315/aamjaf2022.18.2.8>
- Kalembe, D., Kaawaase, T. K., Kayongo, I., Matama, R., & Ngoboka, P. (2024). Audit committee effectiveness and earnings quality: Perception-based evidence from Uganda. *Advances in Research*, 25(1), 78–98. <https://doi.org/10.9734/air/2024/v25i11021>
- Khan, M., Akhtar, S., Afrin, S., & Khan, M. A. (2024). The post-COVID effect of corporate governance on firm performance: A study on private commercial banks in Bangladesh. *Australian Finance & Banking Review*, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.46281/afbr.v8i1.2189>
- Khan, S., Rahman, M., & Thakur, O. (2025). Corporate governance in the banking sector of Bangladesh: Current practices and future prospects. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 25(4), 314–327. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2025/v25i41751>
- Krishnan, G. V., & Visvanathan, G. (2007). Reporting internal control deficiencies in the post-Sarbanes–Oxley era: The role of auditors and corporate governance. *International Journal of Auditing*, 11(2), 73–90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1099-1123.2007.00358.x>
- Kusumosari, L., & Rahardjo, S. N. (2023). Audit committee effectiveness as fraud prevention mechanisms. *Jurnal Riset Akuntansi Dan Bisnis Airlangga*, 8(2), 1602–1623. <https://doi.org/10.20473/jraba.v8i2.51157>
- Lin, J. W., Li, J. F., & Yang, J. S. (2006). The effect of audit committee performance on earnings quality. *Managerial Auditing Journal*, 21(9), 921–933. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02686900610705019>
- Lisic, L. L., Myers, L. A., Seidel, T. A., & Zhou, J. (2019). Does audit committee accounting expertise help to promote audit quality? Evidence from auditor reporting of internal control

- weaknesses. *Contemporary Accounting Research*, 36(4), 2521–2553. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1911-3846.12517>
- Masrick, S., Alamgir, S., Islam, R., & Hasan, M. (2023). Corporate governance and firms' performance: Evidence from Dhaka Stock Exchange. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 28–38. <https://doi.org/10.46281/ijfb.v13i1.1947>
- Mohammadi, S., Saeidi, H., & Naghshbandi, N. (2020). The impact of board and audit committee characteristics on corporate social responsibility: Evidence from the Iranian stock exchange. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 70(8), 2207–2236. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijppm-10-2019-0506>
- Molla, M. I., Islam, M. A., & Rahaman, M. M. (2021). Corporate governance structure and bank performance: Evidence from an emerging economy. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 39(3), 730–746. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jeas-05-2021-0083>
- Oussii, A. A., & Taktak, N. B. (2018). Audit committee effectiveness and financial reporting timeliness. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 9(1), 34–55. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ajems-11-2016-0163>
- Pernamasari, R., & Chariri, A. (2024). Characteristics of the audit committee and the environmental, social, governance (ESG) performance in Indonesian companies. *KNE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i21.16716>
- Purwiyanti, D., & Laksito, H. (2022). The effect of audit committee effectiveness and potential fraudulent financial statements. *Jurnal Aksi (Akuntansi Dan Sistem Informasi)*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.32486/aksi.v7i1.273>
- Raimo, N., Vitolla, F., Marrone, A., & Rubino, M. (2020). Do audit committee attributes influence integrated reporting quality? An agency theory viewpoint. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(1), 522–534. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2635>
- Reaz, M., & Arun, T. (2006). Corporate governance in developing economies: Perspective from the banking sector in Bangladesh. *Journal of Banking Regulation*, 7(1–2), 94–105. <https://doi.org/10.1057/palgrave.jbr.2340007>
- Rifai, M., & Siregar, S. V. (2021). The effect of audit committee characteristics on forward-looking disclosure. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 19(5), 689–706. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfra-05-2019-0063>
- Sarkar, S. (2022). Influence of corporate governance on sustainability disclosure in Bangladesh. *Journal of Management and Research*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.29145/jmr/91/05>
- Uddin, M. N., Hosen, M., Chowdhury, S. R., Chowdhury, M. A., & Mazumder, M. M. (2021). Does corporate governance influence firm value in Bangladesh? A panel data analysis. *E+M Ekonomie a Management*, 24(2), 84–100. <https://doi.org/10.15240/tul/001/2021-2-006>
- Velte, P. (2018). Is audit committee expertise connected with increased readability of integrated reports? Evidence from EU companies. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 16(2), 23–41. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.16\(2\).2018.03](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.16(2).2018.03)
- Weickgenannt, A., Hermanson, D. R., & Sharma, V. D. (2021). How U.S. audit committees oversee internal control over financial reporting. *International Journal of Auditing*, 25(1), 233–248. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijau.12218>

